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Issues of Rural Development in Baksa DistrictJournal of **Social Sciences**

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Abstract:

The study aims to analyze the multifaceted issues of rural development in the Baksa district of Assam, India. Despite governmental efforts and numerous developmental schemes, the region faces challenges that hinder its socio-economic progress. Key areas of concern include poor infrastructure, lack of education, unemployment, and inadequate healthcare facilities. This paper explores these issues and offers insights into potential solutions to address these developmental gaps.

Rural development in Baksa district requires a holistic approach that addresses infrastructure, education, employment, and healthcare challenges. Collaborative efforts between government agencies, non-governmental organizations, and local communities are essential for sustainable development.

Keywords:

Baksa, Rural Development, Bodoland Territorial Region

Introduction

Baksa, a district in the Bodoland Territorial Region of Assam, is predominantly rural and known for its agrarian economy. The district's socio-economic indicators reflect significant disparities in development compared to urban areas. Rural development in Baksa remains critical for achieving sustainable growth and improving the quality of life for its residents. This paper seeks to investigate the primary challenges hindering rural development in the district and identify strategies for their mitigation. (Brahma, V. & Shekhawat, 2016).

Objectives

- To understand the Rural Development mechanism in Baksa district
- To find out the practical issues in regards to rural development
- To find out the challenges of Rural Development in Baksa District

Methodology

The study utilizes a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative data from governmental and non-governmental reports with qualitative insights from interviews and focus group discussions with local stakeholders. Data sources include census records, development reports, and primary data collected through field visits.

Method

The Exploratory and Case Study research methods shall be followed in this study. A case study shall also be conducted in Baksa district interviewing respondents to find out special cases.

Data

The data of the present research work shall include both primary and secondary. The field study method shall also be applied to obtain primary data. Simple Random Sampling method shall be used to collect primary data.

Literature Review

Numerous studies have highlighted the challenges of rural development in Assam and other similar regions. Specific studies focusing on Baksa district remain scarce, necessitating a localized examination of its unique challenges.

About Bodoland Territorial Region and Baksa District

The Bodoland Territorial Council (BTC), constituted under the Sixth Schedule to the Constitution of India mandates to fulfil economic, educational and linguistic aspirations. It also tries to preserve the land-rights, socio-cultural and ethnic identity of Bodo people and to accelerate complete development in BTC area. The Bodoland Territorial Region (BTR) having five districts, viz., Baksa, Chirang, Kokrajhar, Tamulpur and Udalguri. The BTC has placed importance to bring sustainable and fast development in BTR by highlighting three point – Safe Bodoland, Green Bodoland and Smart Bodoland. (Narzary Charan ,2011).

As a result of historic BTC (Bodoland Territorial Council) accord signed on February 10, 2003, formed BTAD (Bodoland Territorial Autonomous District) with four districts namely Kokrajhar, Chirang, Baksa and Udalguri. Baksa district was carved out of Nalbari, Barpeta, Kamrup and a small portion of Darrang district. Baksa district is located in the north-western part of Assam with the district headquarter at Mushalpur, which is 105 Km away from state capital Dispur, Guwahati and 20 Km away from National Highway no. 31 towards north (Das, B. ,2020).

Issues Related to Rural Development in Baksa District

Educational Issues

The acquisition of knowledge and information helps an individual to improve his or her quality of life as well as to participate meaningfully in community life. There are societal benefits too; education is an investment in human capital and leads to higher productivity and earning power. Education helps to achieve social mobility and income redistribution. Studies have shown that increased literacy is associated with improved income share as well as livelihood. (Bora, R., & Gogoi, P.,2020).

Proper education system can make a nation successful by installing respect towards work or making a work culture by inspiring citizens for hard work, increasing capacity of citizen for livelihood etc. For making education system effective government should give priority both in physical capacity like improving infrastructure, providing facilities in schools of the rural areas. In many villages of Baska district, the

education system is suffering from some physical problems like- lack of proper infrastructure of the educational institutions, poor road condition to reach the school, village people are not so aware to send their child to school etc.

Health Issues

Health is another important aspect of rural development of a society. Health is an indicator of well-being that has immediate implications for the quality of life as well as for productive capacities and capabilities. The Constitution of India is uncompromising on the issue of health and the people. It states that the enjoyment of the highest achievable standard of health is one of the fundamental rights of every human being, without distinction of race, religion, political, economic or social condition'. In a declaration adopted by the world community in 1978, and reflected in the Alma Ata declaration of the World Health Organization (WHO), health is classified as a human right. The 'health' of a person or of a group of people is a comprehensive concept that incorporates many dimensions, not just the absence of illness. In fact, the Charter of the World Health Organization (WHO) explicitly defines 'health' as 'a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease and infirmity'. This is a definition that recognizes many dimensions of health and wellbeing, and one that requires action on many different fronts. (Charter of the World Health Organization (WHO), April 7, 1948).

But in some villages of Baksa district, health issues are the main obstacle among the peoples. The peoples suffered from malaria, jaundice, snake biting frequently. But only some PHC (Primary Health Care) centre is available in which no such critical care or treatment is available like 'Anti Venom' injection.

Drinking Water Problems

Drinking water is basic need for an individual for good health. However, in many cases people ignore the importance of drinking water. Access to safe drinking water in Assam is substantially less than the national average. The conditions of Bodoland Territorial Region, especially in Baska district, regarding drinking water is not so good. In many villages of Baska district, arsenic and other harmful chemicals are found in many places while collecting the water sample. Pure drinking water constitutes a basic necessity of the people. In a welfare state, along with primary functions like protection of the security and sovereignty of the states, it should take some other functions for the welfare and development of the people. Provision for drinking water constitutes one among those. And in a situation where consumption of polluted drinking water has given birth to a large number of diseases, government should give necessary attention on building proper water provision. But this is not happening in reality.

Condition of Road and Bridges

Transport system constitutes an important aspect of development of both infrastructure and livelihood. It not only helps in movement of goods and people but also plays an important role in the progress of the society. It is true that government has taken lots of programmes for the development of infrastructure, specially of the transport system. But this is not happening in many village areas of Baska district in real sense of the term. It is true that the urban areas to a great extent have experienced development of the transport system but this is not happening in rural areas.

Flood control

Flood constitutes an important and burning problem of the state as well as of the Bodoland Territorial Region, especially in Baska district. It has made the life of the people miserable. As the rural areas of Baska are agriculturally dominated area, so frequent flood put threats to the livelihood of people. Hence, adequate measures should be adopted to deal with the problem of flood.

Environmental issues (sustainable ways of development)

Development is a ongoing process in everywhere today. But specially in the rural areas of Baska district, new roads are constructed as a part of transportation development. But in this process many old and giant trees are cut by the department persons to make a way to build up new roads. This is not acceptable because cutting of trees in large number causes harm to the rural environment. It is necessary to adopt sustainable development policies for such type of construction related developmental matters.

Findings and Discussion

Infrastructure Deficiency

Infrastructure plays a pivotal role in rural development, yet Baksa faces significant shortcomings in this domain. Roads in many parts of the district are poorly maintained, limiting connectivity and access to markets. Furthermore, the lack of reliable electricity and water supply disrupts daily life and economic activities.

Education and Literacy

Although the district has made strides in improving literacy rates, quality education remains elusive. Schools often lack adequate resources, trained teachers, and infrastructure. According to the Annual Status of Education Report (ASER, 2023), only 45% of students in Baksa achieve grade-appropriate learning outcomes.

Unemployment and Livelihood Challenges

The agrarian economy of Baksa faces challenges such as low productivity, inadequate market linkages, and dependency on traditional farming methods. Youth unemployment is particularly concerning, with limited opportunities for skill development and entrepreneurship. Promoting non-agricultural livelihoods could alleviate this issue (Sharma, 2022).

Healthcare Inequities

Healthcare facilities in Baksa are insufficient to meet the needs of its population. Many villages lack access to primary health centers, forcing residents to travel long distances for medical care. The absence of specialized healthcare services exacerbates the problem, particularly for maternal and child health.

Recommendations

1. **Infrastructure Development:** Investment in road networks, electrification, and clean water supply should be prioritized to enhance connectivity and living standards.
2. **Educational Reforms:** Upgrading school infrastructure, recruiting qualified teachers, and implementing skill-based education programs can improve learning outcomes.
3. **Economic Diversification:** Encouraging non-farm employment through vocational training, small-scale industries, and microfinance initiatives can reduce unemployment.
4. **Healthcare Access:** Establishing more primary health centres and equipping existing facilities with adequate resources can address healthcare disparities.

Conclusion

The present study “Social Science Research and The Study of Rural Development Issues in Baska District” attempted at recounting the journey of rural development in Baksa district of Bodoland Territorial Region. The findings of the study reveal that Baksa has experienced tremendous challenges in providing quality education, good health care, convenient transportation, and sound education system in the rural areas. Rural development is a large area to study, but this study is a try to find out some special issues practically faced by the rural people of Baksa.

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